

VIEWS OF GREAT SCHOLARS, KINGS AND POETS ABOUT THE STRUGGLE

Shermatov G'ulom Kaxxorovich

Senior teacher of the Department of Physical Culture and Sports
Activity, Tashkent Financial Institute
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Abstract: The article analyzes the stages of development of the national struggle, the views of great scholars, kings and poets on the struggle.

Keywords: wrestling, rule, side, national, sport.

The struggle, which attracted the attention of millions and gained fame and popularity, has its deep historical roots as one of the highest spiritual values of the world.

The material evidences found as a result of the researches, researches and archeological researches and observations of historians, antiquarians and philosophers prove that the age of the sport of wrestling is at least 2.5 - 3 thousand years old.

The unique findings, artifacts, and examples of fine art engraved on the rocks, found in Surkhan, Zarafshan oases and a number of ancient settlements of the Fergana valley, testify to this.

There are 6 findings - physical evidence that scientifically prove the history of our struggle. For example, the wall painting of two fighting wrestlers found in Panjikent is considered a unique monument of the Sugdiyana statehood, that is, the medieval period. One such object is a cylinder-shaped ceramic vessel, which was found in ancient Bactria (Southern "Uzbekiston"). One of his pieces depicts two wrestlers and one of them kicking his opponent. In the figurines on the rim of another bowl, wrestlers are shown raising their arms and getting ready to fight. These vessels belong to the Bronze Age, which testifies to the fact that the history of wrestling is even more, that is, 3.5 thousand years ago.

The next find is two horseshoes from the Bronze Age. According to professor M.P. Gryaznov, each horseshoe depicting fighting methods is made in the spirit of the spiritual views of the Sak-Scythian tribes and belongs to the early stages of the nomadic period.

On the surface of the rim of a silver basin dating back to the middle of the first millennium AD, two wrestlers are depicted in the same position as our wrestler.

The objects found in Chelak village near Samarkand also echo from the past. Among these containers with geometric patterns, the package with a silver handle is particularly noteworthy. On the surface of his handle, two wrestlers are fighting in the same Uzbek style of wrestling. This find belongs to the early Middle Ages.

It is no coincidence that Benazir Allama Abu Ali Ibn Sina (980-1037) also emphasized the importance of fighting in the mental and physical condition of a person in his book "Laws of Medicine". According to the great physician, a person who is regularly engaged in physical education will not need treatment for the disease.

Works such as "Shahnoma", "Nightmare", "Boburnoma", which are considered masterpieces of Eastern literature, have bright lines about the character and appearance of wrestlers, and vividly colored images of their non-cultural world.

His Highness Alisher Navoi also enjoyed wrestling, wrestling matches that spread his fame to seven climates. Therefore, in many works, he wrote down wonderful stories and pictures about the life and work of wrestlers. Amir Temur, who built the powerful kingdom of his time, was not only a great statesman, an enlightened ruler, a potential commander, but at the same time, he was also a strong wrestler who perfectly mastered the science of fighting. That's why he attached great importance to training the youth of the country, making them mature individuals who love the country, serve the country, and mature.

In the 9th century AD, the development of wrestling reached a new level. At that time, people living in the territory of modern Uzbekistan used wrestling as a means of entertainment and recreation during traditional holidays, weddings and large public events. Later, wrestling became an independent sport and a method of physical training from a means of entertainment. The strongest wrestlers became famous among the people, and legends began to be woven about them. Pahlavon Mahmud, who lived in the 12th century, is a clear example of this. His grave is still a favorite place of pilgrims and one of the holy places.

In the early 1980s, the famous Uzbek wrestling master, judo fighter and sambo fighter Kamil Yusupov started researching the rich heritage of Uzbek wrestling. The main goal of this breed, one of the activists of the revival of this sport, was to develop new rules of wrestling that correspond to international standards.

By the beginning of the 90s, he successfully fulfilled this honorable task and set himself the goal of bringing Uzbek wrestling to the international arena. At first, he introduced the wrestling rules he had developed to the public, experts, and fans. The new rules incorporate the most honored traditions of Uzbek wrestling and international sports standards such as special uniforms, the place of competition and the duration of the competition.

Sports experts have recognized that the wrestling rules developed by Komil Yusupov fully meet the requirements of international sports. One of the main advantages of wrestling rules is that they do not allow the contest to continue while lying down. As soon as the knee of one of the athletes touches the mat, the referee stops the competition and the wrestlers continue the competition while standing. This ensures that the fight is fast-paced and fun and exciting for the fans.

In addition, the rules of wrestling prohibit the use of techniques that catch the lower part from the belt or cause pain and strangulation. In this way, wrestling has become one of the safest sports that prevent injuries to athletes. The declaration of independence of Uzbekistan in 1991 gave new life to the struggle.

Thousands of wrestlers from different parts of the country have expressed their desire to participate in the competitions, while millions of wrestling fans filled the stadiums across the country eager to enjoy these attractive competitions. The efforts of struggle activists were not limited to Uzbekistan. Since 1992, they have participated in events aimed at promoting Uzbek national wrestling at a number of prestigious sports conferences held in South Korea, Canada, Japan, India, USA, Monaco and Russia.

It can be seen from this that the national struggle is a special delicate craft, a mixture of science and manners, and a harmony, in which there is mutual sincerity, cooperation, harmony, disinterestedness, and friendly attitude between the teacher and the students. defines a lot.

The more thoroughly the teacher can teach his student his knowledge, skills, and the science of national struggle, and if he can direct his efforts towards specific goals, it will certainly bear

fruit. For this, the student should regularly improve his physical training, talent, talent, listen and accept the teacher's teachings with his soul, follow them consistently, and instill the best qualities into his body and soul. this is the term, only then will the qualities such as a worthy succession to our great ancestors, and growing up as a perfect person, be found in it. Every young man or woman who wants to fully learn national wrestling must follow its rules, ethics and moral principles. He should never tarnish the reputation of his homeland and the national struggle with his actions and morals, and he should remain loyal to his people, country, and struggle at all costs until the last minute of his life. In addition, national wrestlers should not talk too much during training or training (if there is no need for it), focus on one place and not look at other things, not to injure each other, even when they are fighting to learn a technique. it is necessary that they immediately inform their partners if there is any defect in each other's wrestling clothes.

References:

1. Tashpulatov F. A., Shermatov G. K. Wrestling-The Honor of Uzbek Nation //Eurasian Scientific Herald. – 2022. – T. 8. – C. 205-208.
2. Alisherovich T. F. Sog'lom turmush tarzini shakillantirishda jismoniy madaniyatning inson hayotidagi roli //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 187-190.
3. Ташпулатов Ф. ГАНДОЛЧИЛАР О'ЙИН FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI HAR TOMONLAMA BAHOLASH METODIKASI //Scienceproblems. uz. – 2023. – T. 3. – №. 1. – C. 96-104.
4. Shermatov G. K. Classification of Methods of Sports Wrestling, System //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 39-42.
5. Мухаметов А.М. (2021) Methodology for Normalizing Workload in Health Classes, european journal of life safety and stability, <http://www.ejlss.indexedresearch.org/>
6. Шерматов Ф.Қ. (2021) DYNAMICS OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS WITH ONE AND TWO TIME COMPULSORY LESSONS, World Economics & Finance Bulletin (WEFB) <https://www.scholarexpress.net/>
7. Мухамметов, А.М. (2022). Научно-методические основы нормирования нагрузок в физкультурно-спортивном здравоохранении. Евразийский научный вестник, 8, 194-197.
8. Khurramovich, K. F. (2022). DEVELOPING A SET OF WELLNESS EXERCISES FOR MIDDLE AGED MEN (45-60 YEARS OLD) ACCORDING TO PHYSICAL PREPARATION. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(04), 165-169.
9. Alisherovich, T. F., & Toshboyeva, M. B. Innovative Pedagogical Activity: Content and Structure.
10. Tashpulatov Farkhad Alisherovich, METHODOLOGY OF COMPREHENSIVE EVALUATION OF GAME ACTIVITY EFFICIENCY OF HANDBALL PLAYERS, 2023/1, ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES, 96-104, <https://doi.org/10.47390/1342V3I1Y2023N10>
11. Khurramovich, K. F. (2022). DEVELOPING A SET OF WELLNESS EXERCISES FOR MIDDLE AGED MEN (45-60 YEARS OLD) ACCORDING TO PHYSICAL PREPARATION. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(04), 165-169.

- 11.Khurramovich, K. F. (2022). METHODOLOGY OF WEIGHTLIFTING WITH ATHLETES. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(4), 1228-1233.
- 12.Karimov, F. X. (2022). Scientific and Methodological Bases of Normalization of Loads in Physical Education and Mass Sports-Health Training. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY, 2(2), 24-28.
- 13.Karimov, F. X. (2021). Plan Individual Fitness Training Programs for Middle-Aged Men. European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630), 11, 238-244.
- 14.Каримов, Ф. Х. (2020). CLASSIFICATION, SYSTEM AND TERMS OF SPORT WRESTLING METHODS. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF DISCOURSE ON INNOVATION, INTEGRATION AND EDUCATION, 1(4), 84-88.
- 15.Каримов, Ф. Х., & Ташпулатов, Ф. А. (2020). РЕСПУБЛИКАМИЗДАГИ ЮНОН-РИМ КУРАШИ БИЛАН ШУҒУЛЛАНУВЧИ ЎСМИРЛАРНИ ҚАРШИ ХУЖУМ УСУЛЛАРИГА ЎРГАТИШ САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШ. ИННОВАЦИИ В ПЕДАГОГИКЕ И ПСИХОЛОГИИ, (SI-2№ 4).
- 16.Каримов, Ф. Х. (2017). Физическая культура и её связь с общей культурой. Высшая школа, (4), 65-66.
- 17.Каримов, Ф. Х. (2017). Физическая культура и её связь с общей культурой. Высшая школа, (4), 65-66.
- 18.Karimov, F. K. (2022). Developing A Combination of Health Exercises for Middle-Aged Men Aged 45-60. Eurasian Scientific Herald, 8, 201-204.
- 19.Tashbaeva, M. (2022). Pedagogical Opportunities of Wrestling Sports in the Formation of a Sense of National Pride in Students. Eurasian Scientific Herald, 8, 213-216.
- 20.Toshboyeva, M. B. (2022). WELLNESS EXERCISES FOR HUMAN ENDURANCE DEVELOPMENT. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(4), 1214-1220.
- 21.Toshboyeva, M. B. (2022). Wrestling is a Kind of Sport with an Example of the First Training jar the Importance of the Formation of FastPaced Power Attributes with the Help of Moving Games. Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies, 6, 291-294.
- 22.<https://iejrd.com/index.php/%20/article/view/2965>
- 23.<https://iejrd.com/index.php/%20/article/view/2962>

